

KANDHAMAL MARTYRS

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Abstract: The “Kandhamal martyrs” are bold Jesus-witnesses with their rock-like faith. They testify to the good news of Jesus Christ with the “pouring out of blood.” Their firm faith, courageous response in persecution, reconciling forgiveness, and communitarian witness make them paradigms of Gospel-praxis. Their *martyria* resonates that of the early Christians. As Spirit-filled and bold witnesses of Jesus Christ for our times, they inspire us to preach the Gospel courageously in faithful imitation of the Master (cf. Lk 6:40).

Keywords: Kandhamal, *martyria*, Kantheswar Digal, Jesus-Witness, Martyrdom.

INTRODUCTION

This series, titled “GOSPEL in ACTION,” sheds light on Jesus’ witnesses who by their deeds culminating in the “pouring out of blood” (cf. Lk 22:20; Acts 22:20) testify to the good news of the risen Lord Jesus Christ.¹ The “Kandhamal martyrs” are bold Jesus-witnesses with their “rock-like faith” manifest during the

¹ The twelve Jesus-witnesses introduced in the Series, “GOSPEL in ACTION,” in 2026 are: Devasahayam, Rani Maria, Kandhamal martyrs, John de Britto, Mathew Mannaparambil, James Kottayil, Stan Swamy, Herman Rasschaert, Arul Doss, AT Thomas, Valsa John, and Tom Gafney. Each of these twelve proclaims the Gospel with a Spirit-guided praxis. The *Acts of the Apostles* and *When the Gospel Grows Feet*, a biography on Rutilio Grande, inspire the series-title “GOSPEL in ACTION.” In presenting each Jesus-witness, there is (1) a brief introduction to the martyr and their contextual Gospel praxis, and (2) a concise exposition to a defining characteristic of witnessing (*martyria*).

severe persecution and anti-Christian violence in Kandhamal district of Odisha in 2008.² Carrying their cross, they follow the crucified Lord faithfully and, thus, testify to the good news of the risen Lord Jesus Christ with the “pouring out of blood.” Their witness (*martyria*) resonates that of the early Christians.

1. BOLD WITNESS AMID PERSECUTION

“It is only because of Jesus that I survived... They fired so many bullets at me. But look, no one hit my heart. Is it not a miracle?” – thus responds Junos Nayak, a survivor of Kandhamal persecution, to Anto Akkara’s question whether he still believes that ‘Jesus is the Saviour.’³ Junos’ elder brother Lalji was shot dead in the same attack at Gadaguda on 30 September 2008. He is one among the many in Odisha’s Kandhamal district who are “prepared to forsake everything for their faith at the ground zero of the worst persecution of Christians in Indian history.”⁴ During the severe persecution from August to December 2008, “more than 600 villages were ransacked, 5600 houses were looted and burnt, 54000 people were left homeless and 38 people were murdered. Human rights groups estimate that over 100 people were killed, including disabled and elderly persons, children and women.”⁵

² I am indebted to Late Bimal (Kiran) Nayak IMS whose B.Th. Dissertation at Vidyajyoti in 2014 on his own people, the persecuted Christians of Kandhamal, introduced me to the shining faith of Kandhamal. Later, celebrating the Sunday liturgy on 11 May 2014 in his Pokari parish in Kandhamal and staying at his home offered me memorable first-hand experiences of the vibrant faith and of the caring community of Kandhamal. My sincere gratitude also to Ashish Digal SJ, a Jamshedpur Jesuit doing his second year B.Th. at Vidyajyoti at present, for narrating to me his own experience, as a hostel student in Raikia, of being stranded in Kandhamal forest for three days during the severe persecution in 2008. Ashish’s brother Devashish Digal faced a near-death moment during the 2008 violence when an enraged mob caught him, shaved his head in preparation for *reconversion*, and was led to be sacrificed as he was unwilling to recant his faith. Devashish’s Hindu friend’s father saved him from the mob.

³ Cf. Anto Akkara, *Early Christians of the 21st Century: Stories of Incredible Christian Witness from Kandhamal Jungles* (Thrissur: Veritas India Books, 2015), 255.

⁴ *Ibid.*, 254.

⁵ Vahida Nainar and Vrinda Grover (eds.), *Waiting for Justice: A Report of*

The “Kandhamal martyrs” refers particularly to a group of 35 Christians, Servant of God Kantheswar Digal and his 34 companions, who are killed during the anti-Christian violence since August 2008 in Kandhamal district.⁶ The Vatican’s Dicastery for the Causes of Saints has given *nihil obstat* to open a beatification cause for the Kandhamal martyrs, clearing the way for a diocesan investigation into their lives, deaths, and witness to faith.⁷ For many in the local Christian

National People’s Tribunal on Kandhamal (New Delhi: National Solidarity Forum, 2011), 9. This Report states further that “an unestimated number suffered severe physical injuries and mental trauma. While there are reports of a few women being sexually assaulted, many more such victims are believed to have been intimidated into silence. 295 churches and other places of worship, big and small, were destroyed. 13 schools, colleges, and offices of several non-profit organizations damaged. About 30,000 people were uprooted and lived in relief camps and continue to be displaced.” Ibid.; see also, Anto Akkara, *Kandhamal: A Blot on Indian Secularism* (Delhi: Media House, 2009), 15.

⁶ The 35 “Kandhamal martyrs” are Kantheswar Digal, Father Bernard Digal, Juboraj Digal, Sibino Pradhan, Raghupati Digal, Bikram Nayak, Rajesh Digal, Trinath Digal, Parikhita Nayak, Suchitra Digal, Lensa Digal, Subedana Nayak, Mayagini Digal, Jhunima Parichha, Bastina Montry, Priya Darshoni Nayak, Dustina Parichha, Sirel Parichha, Bhumika Digal, Tepan Nayak, Badani Digal, Digamber Digal, Lalita Digal, Augustine Digal, Tileswar Paltasingh, Kundan Montry, Hemant Digal, Bibhisana Digal, Reboti Parichha, Melanio Digal, Krushna Nayak, Jamadei Pradhan, Baliarsingh Digal, Gonda Digal, and Mary Pani. Cf. Shireen Bhatia, “Vatican Approves Beatification Process for Martyrs of Kandhamal Anti-Christian Violence,” 27 October 2023, *Christian Today*, <https://www.christiantoday.co.in/news/vatican-approves-beatification-process-for-martyrs-of-kandhamal-anti-christian-violence.html> (accessed on 24.01.2026). Dibakar Parichha and Santosh Kumar Digal narrate 19 incidents connected with these Servants of God in *Kandhamal: Massacre of the Innocents* (New Delhi: Integrity Media, 2015).

⁷ On 18 October 2023, Archbishop Leopoldo Girelli, the Apostolic Nuncio in India, forwards the letter from the Dicastery for the Causes of Saints to Archbishop John Barwa of Cuttack-Bhubaneswar and states that “in response to your letter, dated 31 May 2023, the said Dicastery is granting you the *Nihil Obstat* to initiate the process of beatification for the Servant of God Kantheswar Digal and companions, martyrs of Kandhamal, “*Normis servandis in Inquisitionibus ab Episcopis faciendis in Causis Sanctorum.*” Subsequently, the diocesan inquiry compiles biographies, witness statements, and evidence of sanctity. This compilation has been challenging because many martyrs come from tribal and Dalit backgrounds with limited documentation.

community and human rights advocates, the move is both a spiritual recognition of the sacrifice of the bold martyrs and a symbolic step toward remembering them and seeking justice and reconciliation for the survivors of the 2008 persecution.

The “shining faith in Kandhamal” serves as both the salt and light (cf. Mt 5:13-14) for the present.⁸ Indeed, “the valiant Christians of Kandhamal, with their incredible and heroic witness, have provided the catacomb experience to Indian Christians at the dawn of the third millennium.”⁹ Persecution does strengthen one’s faith. The emboldened Christian community in Kandhamal resists the threats of fundamentalists to recant its faith. The words of Kanakrekha Nayak, with her four-year old daughter, at Udaigiri Refugee Camp in January 2009 manifest how the community is anchored on the risen Lord: “I cannot think of giving up my faith. My husband sacrificed his life for the faith in Jesus. Whatever may happen, I will never give up my faith.”¹⁰ The Kandhamal community walks the way of the cross faithfully by taking up their cross and following the crucified Lord (cf. Mt 16:24). Like the apostles, they rejoice that they are “considered worthy to suffer dishonor for the sake of the name” (Acts 5:41). Archbishop John Barwa’s words during his pastoral visit to Padangi parish in Kandhamal in 2012 are apt in describing their exemplary witness: “I would call my people ‘God’s own people’ for their amazing

⁸ According to Udaynath Bishoyi, “Christian faith from the perspective of the persecuted Kandhamal church symbolically represents ‘flames of faith’ which cannot become extinct from the hearts and hills of Kandhamal; rather it shall continue to glow, refine and dispel the darkness of sinful forces and evil forms and structures.” Udaynath Bishoyi, *Flames of Faith in Kandhamal: A Christological Reading of the Suffering, Hope and Mission of the People of Kandhamal* (Bhubaneswar: Shades Publications, 2018), 23.

⁹ This is the opening line of a video-documentary series titled “Kandhamal: the Living Face of God,” directed by Anto Akkara, and produced by Atmadarshan TV, Indore. Cf. “Rock-like Faith of Kandhamal,” August 31, 2022, 26:08, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=t3aZl9BusQ4> (accessed on 24.01.2026).

¹⁰ Ibid.

witness to Christ.”¹¹ He adds, “God’s plans are beyond our comprehension. What happened here was very painful. It is turning out to be a blessing.”

2. *MARTYRIA* (WITNESS, MARTYRDOM)

The term “witness” (*martyrs* in Greek) refers, in religious context, to “a person who has given or exposed [one’s] life in testimony to the truth or relevance of the Christian faith.”¹² This religious nuance is derived from its basic meaning as “one who remembers, who has knowledge of something by recollection, and who can thus tell about it.”¹³ In the context of Acts, a “witness” is a person who testifies to the message of the resurrection of Lord Jesus Christ. Acts affirms that the resurrection of the exalted Lord is the focus of “witness” (cf. 1:22; 2:32; 3:15; 4:33; 5:31-32; 10:40-41; 13:30-31). There has been a transition from the juridical meaning of “witness,” as a legal testimony, to “martyr,” as one who testifies to the risen Lord Jesus Christ.¹⁴

In the Jewish Tradition, “witness” (*martyrs*) belongs to the legal sphere in the LXX.¹⁵ *Martyrs* occurs some 60 times denoting “witness before the judgment,” and “one that has personal knowledge of an event or a fact.”¹⁶ In the Jewish

¹¹ Ibid. Highlighting both the severe persecution and the community’s forgiveness, Premanand Nayak comments that “over a long period of time the Christians there [in Kandhamal] have been turning cheek after cheek and paying for the assaults on them because of their steadfast faith in their religion.” Premanand Nayak, *In Kandhamal: There are No More Cheeks to Turn* (Delhi: Media House, 2015), 20.

¹² F. X. Murphy and W. F. Dicharry, “Martyr,” in *New Catholic Encyclopedia*, vol. 9, ed. Thomas Carson and Joann Cerrito (Detroit, MI: Thomson Gale, 2003), 226.

¹³ Hermann Strathmann, “μάρτυς,” *TDNT*, 4:475.

¹⁴ Cf. Rino Fisichella, “Martyr,” in *Dictionary of Fundamental Theology*, ed. René Latourelle and Rino Fisichella (New York, NY: Crossroad, 1994), 624.

¹⁵ The word for “witness” in the Septuagint (LXX), *martyrs*, “signifies first of all one who bears witness before a judgment is made, especially the witness for the prosecution (Num. 5:13; 35:30; Deut. 17:6f.; 19:15).” Allison A. Trites, *The New Testament Concept of Witness*, Society for New Testament Studies 31 (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1977), 16.

¹⁶ Defining a witness to be “one that has personal knowledge of an event or a fact,” Haim H. Cohn comments that “Jewish law distinguishes between attesting

faith, martyrdom represents “the extreme opportunity within the realm of the humanly possible for the individual believer [such as Eleazar and the seven brothers (2 Macc 6–7), or Daniel and his friends (Dan 3ff)] to prove his belief in Yahweh” courageously.¹⁷ The writings of Flavius Josephus and Philo of Alexandria, both contemporary with the New Testament, contain many uses of the idea of “witness” in legal contexts and in legal metaphors.¹⁸ Both Josephus and Philo refer to “witness to fact” and “God as a witness” (divine witness) and help one “see the links between the Old and the New Testament ideas of witness.”¹⁹

In the Greco-Roman context of Jesus’ times, a “witness” (*martyrs*) in a Greek legal court is called in for testimony, similar to what is practised already in Mesopotamian law, to support truth in legal matters.²⁰ Besides the legal and testimonial contexts, it is also used in a religious sense where gods are invoked as witnesses in oaths and treaties.²¹ This transition affirms the metaphorical extension of the meaning of *martyrs*. However, the evidential value of testimony in Greek courts of law, unlike that in the Jewish tradition, is relatively low. The term “witness” in ancient Roman literature originates from the Latin word *testis*, which evolves into concepts central to legal, social, and literary contexts.²² The witnesses are necessary for the validity of a trial.

[formal legal acts] and testifying [to an act previously attested] witnesses.” Haim H. Cohn, “Witness,” in *Encyclopaedia Judaica*, ed. Fred Skolnik, 2nd ed. (Detroit, MI: Thomson Gale, 2007), 21:115.

¹⁷ Cf. Hans Urs von Balthasar, *The Moment of Christian Witness*, trans. Richard Beckley (New York, NY: Newman Press, 1969), 10.

¹⁸ Cf. Trites, *New Testament Concept of Witness*, 57.

¹⁹ *Ibid.*, 65.

²⁰ Cf. S. C. Todd, *The Shape of Athenian Law* (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1993), 96.

²¹ In Homer’s *Iliad*, in Book 3 (line 350), characters call upon Zeus or other deities to sanctify agreements towards the truce between Greeks and Trojans: “bear witness ye, And keep unbroken this day’s promises.” Cf. *The Iliad of Homer*, trans. William C. Bryant (Cambridge: Riverside Press, 1898), 3:79.

²² Cf. Adolf Berger, “Testis,” in *Encyclopedic Dictionary of Roman Law* (Philadelphia, PA: American Philosophical Society, 1953), 735.

In the New Testament, especially in Acts, *martyrs* is used as a witness both in the general and legal senses (cf. Mk 14:56.59.63; Lk 22:71) and to the facts of Christ's life, especially to the resurrection (Lk 24:48; Acts 1:8). In Acts 4:33, Luke uses it for those who testify to the risen Lord Jesus Christ: "with great power, the apostles gave their witness to the resurrection of Jesus Christ." However, his use of *martyrs* in Acts 22:20, where he makes Paul describe Stephen as "Jesus' witness," signifies both its basic meaning, i.e., the testimony to the truth of Jesus' resurrection, and its extended post-NT meaning, i.e., the testimony to the resurrection involving death. Here, *martyrs* is used in the sense of "a true witness" who is "conceived to be an imitator of Jesus Christ."²³ Thus, being a "witness" (*martyrs*), in the NT sense, is "the very essence of the Christian vocation."²⁴ The NT understanding of *martyrs* involves "a metaphorical application of the legal term."²⁵ Overall, the Lukan portrayal of Stephen as *martyrs* exemplifies the NT use of "witness" as both one who testifies to the resurrection of Jesus Christ and one who dies for the same testimony. The "Kandhamal martyrs" continue the legacy of early Christianity in close imitation of the crucified and risen Lord Jesus Christ (cf. Lk 6:40).

²³ James M. Boice, *Witness and Revelation in the Gospel of John* (Exeter: Paternoster Press, 1970), 165.

²⁴ Fisichella, "Martyr," 629.

²⁵ Robert P. Casey, "Μάρτυς," in *The Beginnings of Christianity 1: The Acts of the Apostles*, vol. 5, *Additional Notes to the Commentary*, ed. Kirsopp Lake and Henry J. Cadbury (Grand Rapids, MI: Baker Book House, 1966), 31. Casey analyzes the occurrences of μάρτυς in Acts 1:8 and Lk 24:48 to show the metaphorical transition of the meaning of *martyrs* from "a witness at trial" to "a testimony to the resurrection." Cf. *ibid.*, 31-32. Karl Rahner acknowledges the origins of the concept of martyrdom that "led to the accepted meaning: a martyr is one who freely accepting his death in faith... bears a noble testimony as 'witness' to faith in Jesus Christ." Karl Rahner, "On Martyrdom," in *On the Theology of Death*, 2nd ed. (New York, NY: Herder and Herder, 1967), 82. Tracing the semantic history of *martyrs* in the NT, Cornelius Ekka opines that "only a long process would lead to identifying the martyr with someone who becomes a witness to the faith to the point of giving up his/her life." Cornelius Ekka, "Martyrdom as Witness and Memory: A Study of the Theology of Martyrdom in the Early and Contemporary Christian Writings" (Master's thesis, Vidyajyoti College of Theology, Delhi, 2008), 5.

APOSTOLIC NUNCIATURE
IN INDIA

New Delhi, 18 October 2023

N. 4366/23/IN

Your Grace,

I am pleased to forward to you the enclosed letter, Prot. N. 3683-1/23, dated 2 October 2023, from the Dicastery for the Causes of Saints (Enclosure).

In response to your letter, dated 31 May 2023, the said Dicastery is granting you the *Nihil Obstat* to initiate the process of beatification for the Servant of God Kanteshwar Digal and companions, martyrs of Khandamal, "*Normis servandis in Inquisitionibus ab Episcopis faciendis in Causis Sanctorum*".

With my prayerful regards, I remain,

Yours fraternally in Christ,

Archbishop Leopoldo Girelli,
Apostolic Nuncio

His Grace

Most Rev. John BARWA, S.V.D.

Archbishop of Cuttack-Bhubaneswar

Archbishop's

BHUBANESHWAR - 751 007

(With Enclosure)

CONCLUSION

Witnessing to the gospel of Lord Jesus Christ, the “Kandhamal martyrs” live exemplary lives that culminate in the “pouring out of blood.” Their bold response to severe persecution inspires the present generation of Jesus-disciples to face contemporary crises. The fact that there has not been any revenge-killing in Kandhamal, from the part of Kandhamal Christians, is an enduring legacy to the Lord’s command to love and to forgive. It also manifests their cohesive and caring community (*koinonia*). Amidst the threats to recant their faith, they remain anchored on the risen Lord Jesus Christ. Thus, their *martyria* of faith continues to shine as it proclaims the hope of the kingdom of God.

Book Reviews

Book Review Editor: Anil D’Almeida SJ

Towards Living Christologies in the World. By A. Alangaram. Bengaluru: ATC, 2024. ISBN: 978-81-19664-65-8. Pp. xxix + 181. Price: ₹300.

Towards Living Christologies in the World emerges from the author’s personal experience of living among the poor and marginalized Panaiyeri Nadars in Tamil Nadu and sharing in their struggles for dignity and rights along with other priests. This lived experience becomes the interpretive lens of the entire work. Alangaram begins with the conviction that the Christ event occurred once in human history within a specific socio-political, economic, religious, and cultural context. Yet he raises a theological question: how do people across the world hear the words

of Jesus of Nazareth and follow him within their diverse and changing situations of life? From this question arises his central thesis that changing contexts inevitably produce multiple Christological expressions, each meaningful within its own historical and cultural location. The book is therefore divided into two major parts: Part One, consisting of five chapters, examines the emergence of living Christologies across continents, while Part Two, comprising three chapters, reflects on following Jesus in the liberation of humanity.

The foundational argument of the book is that critical reflection on life experiences and praxis in Christ gives birth to what the author calls “living Christologies.” These are contextual and peo-